

Hybrid deep neural networks for detection of non-technical losses in electricity smart meters

Madalina-Mihaela Buzau, *Student Member, IEEE*, Javier Tejedor-Aguilera, Pedro Cruz-Romero, *Member, IEEE*, and Antonio Gómez-Expósito, *Fellow, IEEE*,

Abstract—Non-technical losses in electricity utilities are responsible for major revenue losses. In this paper, we propose a novel end-to-end solution to self-learn the features for detecting anomalies and frauds in smart meters using a hybrid deep neural network. The network is fed with simple raw data, removing the need of handcrafted feature engineering. The proposed architecture consists of a long short-term memory network and a multi-layer perceptrons network. The first network analyses the raw daily energy consumption history whilst the second one integrates non-sequential data such as its contracted power or geographical information. The results show that the hybrid neural network significantly outperforms state-of-the-art classifiers as well as previous deep learning models used in non-technical losses detection. The model has been trained and tested with real smart meter data of Endesa, the largest electricity utility in Spain.

Index Terms—Supervised learning, hybrid neural networks, non-technical losses, smart meter data.

I. INTRODUCTION

NON-technical losses (NTL) in electricity utilities are defined as the energy consumption (EC) delivered but not recorded by the utility [1]. These losses, also known as commercial losses, can be caused either by theft, faults in the meters or billing irregularities [2], [3]. Regardless of their source, they are accountable for important revenue losses and have a negative impact on the grid reliability [4].

Worldwide, a recent report has estimated that NTL are responsible for yearly revenue losses of \$96 billion [5]. At the grid level, NTL can affect the power system operation by overloading transformers and causing voltage unbalances [4], [6]. Thus, reducing NTL will also reduce the physical losses of the grid [7]. Moreover, the costs of on-field inspections made to recover these losses, debt collection and even court costs in some cases, have to be taken into consideration as well. The low effectiveness of these inspections can further increase the NTL cost. Hence, it is extremely important for the utilities to advance in this field and increase the success rate of future on-field inspections for an efficient revenue loss recovery.

NTL detection is a complex anomaly detection task. Relying solely on outlier detection methods (e.g. k-means clustering, local outlier factor) is neither sufficient nor reliable for accurate predictions. EC patterns can change due to multiple factors and only a few of those changes are due to NTL. The

main challenge of the algorithm is to recognize these NTL patterns among all of them.

In this paper, we propose an end-to-end solution for NTL detection using a hybrid neural network, requiring minimal input data and no domain knowledge of the problem. The architecture proposed in this paper outperforms state-of-the-art classifiers as well as previous deep learning approaches. The daily EC profile is analyzed through a long short-term memory network (LSTM) whilst the non-sequential data are passed through a multi-layer perceptrons (MLP) network. By combining these two networks, major improvements in the performance have been obtained. The model has been trained and tested on real smart meter (SM) data of the largest electricity utility in Spain, Endesa.

A. Related work

The current NTL detection algorithms fall into three categories: data-oriented, network-oriented and hybrid-oriented, which is a mix between both [8]. Network-oriented approaches such as the methodology described in [9], use Distribution State Estimation (DSE) algorithms to search for irregular cases of EC. Hybrid-oriented methodologies use DSE algorithms combined with statistics or machine learning algorithms. A hybrid approach has been proposed in [10], where the authors use DSE and analysis of variance (ANOVA) for NTL detection. The DSE is used to detect distribution transformers with anomalous usage using the normalized residual test. After identifying transformers with anomalous usage, the NTL is detected at the customer level using ANOVA. Another hybrid NTL methodology is proposed in [11], which uses DSE and an Optimum-Path Forest (OPF) classifier. The DSE is used to estimate the NTL in each month at the bus level. These NTL estimations are added to the input of the OPF classifier which was trained in a supervised manner on a synthetic dataset. Network and hybrid approaches can detect NTL cases with a high precision but they cannot be easily implemented in the utility as they require knowledge of the network topology and parameters as well as the installation of additional metering devices.

Data-oriented approaches focus only on the data provided by the SMs, requiring no knowledge of the network topology and no additional hardware devices. The solution proposed in this paper is a data-driven approach based on supervised learning, using data from previous on-field NTL inspections. Previous NTL detection methods that fall into this category [2], [12], [13], [14], [15], apart from being very expensive,

Madalina-Mihaela Buzau, Pedro Cruz-Romero and Antonio Gómez-Expósito are with the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Seville, Spain. Javier Tejedor Aguilera is with Endesa-Enel, Seville. Corresponding author: Madalina-Mihaela Buzau (email: madbuz@alum.us.es).

require specific human expert knowledge far from being complete in practical terms. Moreover, though the SMs rollout improves the performance in NTL detection, they also introduce new methods for energy theft [16]. This makes it more difficult for detection algorithms based on expert knowledge to adapt to new types of frauds. Therefore, the problem of NTL detection is still not solved satisfactorily.

MLP networks have been previously implemented in NTL detection methodologies, but the majority of them have not been used with the purpose of replacing expert knowledge. As an example, the methodology described in [17] uses a MLP network to estimate the hyperparameters of a support vector machines (SVM) classifier, in order to maximize the accuracy of its predictions for NTL detection. The authors in [18] used statistical techniques and unsupervised neural networks (Kohonen networks), as two separate methodologies, for NTL detection. The Kohonen networks were used to cluster customers based on their EC pattern. In [19], the authors used text mining techniques to extract concepts from inspectors' comments of previous on-field inspections. After manually labeling 1% of the extracted concepts, a MLP network has been used for training and for classifying the rest of the concepts. MLP networks have been used as end-to-end models for NTL detection, in [20] and [21].

New methodologies based on deep learning have been proposed recently, such as the work described in [22], where the authors compared the performance of a convolutional neural network (CNN), a stacked autoencoder and a LSTM for the task of NTL detection. The results showed that the CNN outperformed the rest of the classifiers, on a synthetic dataset. Another deep learning methodology has been proposed in [23], where a CNN and a MLP network are used on raw EC data. However, CNN and MLP networks cannot work with sequential data such as the EC history, limiting the input to a fixed size window for all samples. For example, if the input is limited to EC data of the previous year, the model cannot capture a descent in the EC consumption if it happened before the period of analysis. Furthermore, as we will show further, simply analyzing the EC on a real dataset, with real NTL samples, does not yield optimal results due to the nature of this problem.

The main contributions of the paper are as follows:

- We propose a state-of-the-art methodology for NTL detection that can self-learn features that are relevant for NTL detection. This methodology can integrate both sequential and non-sequential data. To our knowledge, this is the first deep learning architecture for NTL detection that is able to accommodate both types of data.
- We investigate the boost in performance obtained by combining both types of data and show that the hybrid network significantly outperforms a network that uses only EC data as an input.
- We show that the proposed architecture vastly outperforms previous NTL detection models that were based on deep learning and raw data. We also compare its performance with state-of-the-art classifiers and their learning capabilities with raw SM data.

Contrary to [23] and [22], in this paper the precision of new on-field inspections guided by our proposed model is reported. The precision is the fraction of SMs that were actually identified with NTL, among the total number of SMs that have been inspected using the ranked list of customers provided by our model. This methodology is currently used as an NTL detection tool in the utility, achieving a precision of $\approx 47\%$ for new on-field inspections generated by our model. This represents a 3.5 times improvement over the precision of previous on-field inspections that have been generated through other tools and campaigns.

II. MOTIVATION

Several types of fraudulent customer-related NTL are reported by utilities throughout the world [1]. Figure 1 shows the EC history of specific Spanish SMs found with NTL in their meters. Figure 1.a shows the EC profile of a SM that was directly tampered with a shunt device between the input and output terminals of the SM to divert the current. An example of a double tapping fraud is shown in Figure 1.b. Double tapping is a typical fraud case, where part of the consumption is connected directly to the grid, bypassing the SM. In this particular case, the fraud occurred from the beginning of the contract, so a descent in the consumption cannot be observed. Figure 1.c shows the case of a SM found with an electronic fault, a common cause of anomaly in SMs.

Fig. 1. Real NTL cases (Source: Endesa)

Though in all NTL cases the meters report lower EC readings, the change in the consumption profile is manifested differently depending on the NTL source. Traditional approaches aim to capture the behavior of different types of NTL using handcrafted feature engineering, as there is no mathematical formulation for the EC pattern of a SM with a shunt or double tapping. With this approach, a set of features that aim to characterize each type of anomaly or fraud is created. For example, features that detect a sudden drop in consumption are aimed to detect shunts or double tapping cases. In the case of electronic faults, features that monitor

the number of zero measurements or number of missing measurements are employed. Unfortunately, these approaches rely heavily on expert knowledge which is very expensive and time-consuming. Moreover, they require experts to develop continuously new features in order to adapt to new types of NTL. To mitigate the constraints of previous approaches, we propose a deep learning architecture that is able to self-learn these features from raw EC measurements and that can adapt automatically to new NTL behavior in the SM data.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 shows the methodology proposed in this paper for NTL detection. The methodology has been developed and tested on a real dataset of an electricity utility. This methodology needs as an input three types of data: EC history recorded by the SMs, auxiliary data (geographical, contracts, technical and economic data) and the results of previous on-field inspections along with their dates. The SM data is used to create the LSTM input whilst the auxiliary data is used for the MLP input.

The first step is to create customer samples. The methodology for creating customer samples is the same as in [15]. By using the results of previous on-field inspections, the first and last day of each customer sample can be extracted following the rules presented in Figure 3. For customers who never had an inspection their sample represents their entire consumption history. The processed dataset is split further based on whether a customer sample has been previously inspected or not. This creates a labeled and unlabeled dataset. The unlabeled dataset consists of samples belonging to customers who were never inspected or whose normalization date was more than 365 days ago. The labeled dataset is used to train the model in a supervised manner, using the results of previous on-field inspections. This dataset is split further into a training, validation and test dataset in order to assess the performance of the model on samples that have not been seen during training.

Data processing techniques have been used on all datasets. A thorough description of these techniques can be found in Section V-B. During model selection, the best hyperparameters of the model are selected using the validation dataset. The final performance is assessed on the test dataset. If the model performance on the test dataset is acceptable for the utility, the trained model is used to make predictions on the unlabeled dataset, creating a ranked list of customers to be inspected based on their probabilities of having NTL in their SM.

A. Model architecture of the hybrid neural network

The model proposed in this paper is a hybrid neural network (HNN-NTL), capable of integrating both sequential and non-sequential SM information. The architecture of the HNN-NTL model can be found in Figure 4. The network consists of three modules: the LSTM module, the MLP module and the hybrid module. The LSTM module uses the sequential data of the SM (e.g. EC), whilst the MLP module uses the non-sequential data as an input (e.g. SM location, model). The outputs of the LSTM module and the MLP module are afterwards used as an input to the hybrid module which provides the

Fig. 2. Methodology outline for NTL detection

Fig. 3. Scenario of a customer with multiple training samples.

final probability of having an NTL in the SM. This type of architecture is very efficient as it permits joint training on both types of input. A detailed description of each module is presented in the following subsections.

B. Long short-term memory module for sequential data

Table I shows the input features that get fed into the LSTM model at each time step. Though the SM records the hourly EC, we have reduced the granularity of measurements to the daily level as we have seen through experiments that it yields better results than hourly measurements. The daily EC has been obtained by simply averaging the hourly ECs in a day. The weekend ECs were removed using the time stamp of each SM measurement. Thus, the weekly profile consisted of

Fig. 4. HNN-NTL model architecture

5 measurements of the daily average consumption at each time step.

TABLE I
LSTM INPUT AT EACH TIME STEP

Input	Description	Size
Weekly profile	Daily energy consumption of the weekdays.	5
Zero measurements	Number of 0 kWh measurements in each weekday.	5
Missing measurements	Number of null measurements in each weekday.	4
Season	The season of the week.	4

Since the EC history recorded by the SMs can be years long and it is increasing day by day, a simple recurrent neural network [24] cannot be used as it would be very hard to train due to their vanishing and exploding gradient problems [25]. Thus, to capture the long-term dependencies in the variable-sized EC data an LSTM cell has been used [26]. The LSTM cell uses the sigmoid $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$ and the hyperbolic tangent $\tanh(x) = \frac{e^{2x}-1}{e^{2x}+1}$ as nonlinear activations and it has the following mathematical formulation:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (1)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (2)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (3)$$

$$C_t = f_t \odot C_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tanh(W_c x_t + U_c h_{t-1} + b_c) \quad (4)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \quad (5)$$

where i_t , f_t , o_t , C_t and h_t represent the activations of the input gate, forget gate, output gate, cell state and hidden state at time step t . W_i , W_f , W_o and W_c represent the weights of the input layer whilst U_i , U_f , U_o and U_c represent the recurrent weights of the LSTM. b_i , b_f , b_o , b_c are the biases of the network whilst x_t is the input features vector at time step t and

h_{t-1} represents the hidden state activation at the previous time step. \odot represents the element-wise multiplication (Hadamard product).

The LSTM module sees the entire EC history, week by week, and it provides a single final output, h_T , which is the hidden state of the LSTM cell at the final time step (last week of the sample). We decided to use the weekly profile as input to the LSTM, rather than the daily consumption, in order to reduce the number of time steps through the network. By reducing the number of time steps, the network is able to learn faster. Using the weekly profile gives the network the opportunity to detect more complex types of NTL, such as intermittent NTL, which occurs only on some certain days of the week. These cases would be much more difficult to detect when using only the monthly EC as an input.

C. Multi-layer perceptrons module for non-sequential data

The MLP network is used to analyze the non-sequential data. The metadata that has been used in this module can be found in Table II. Input features that are continuous have a size of 1 whilst categorical features have a higher dimension. We used entity embeddings [27] for the categorical variables, instead of one-hot-encoding, in order to reduce the input space of the MLP network. For example, only the economic activity code has 473 unique categories.

The MLP module has N hidden layers, where N is chosen using the validation dataset. Each hidden layer goes through an affine transformation ($n > 0$):

$$z_n = W_n h_{n-1} + b_n \quad (6)$$

where W_n represents the weights of layer n , h_{n-1} represents the hidden state of the previous layer and b_n represents the bias of the n_{th} layer.

TABLE II
MLP INPUT DATA

Type of data	Input	Size
Geographical data	Latitude	1
	Longitude	1
	Altitude	1
	Municipality	5
Contract data	Contracted power	1
	Contract type	2
	Voltage	1
SM technical data	SM model	3
	SM location	3
	SM firmware version	3
	SM production year	3
Economic data	Economic activity code	10

To speed up the convergence of the network, a batch normalization layer [28] has been used on the affine transformation:

$$b_n = \gamma \hat{z}_n + \beta \quad (7)$$

where \hat{z}_n represents the standardized affine activation with the mean and standard deviation of the batch sample and γ and β are trainable parameters that are tuned during optimization.

The final state of the hidden layer is obtained by using a rectified linear unit:

$$h_n = \max(0, b_n) \quad (8)$$

D. Hybrid module

The hidden state h_{LSTM} of the hybrid module has been obtained using as an input the hidden state of the LSTM cell h_T at the final time step (T is the sequence length). Similarly, the hidden state h_{MLP} has been computed using as an input the hidden state activations of the last hidden layer in the MLP module h_N . Both h_{LSTM} and h_{MLP} have been computed using transformations described in the equations (6), (7) and (8).

The hybrid module simply takes afterwards the hidden states h_{LSTM} and h_{MLP} and concatenates them in order to form a new hidden layer.

The final state of the HNN-NTL model is obtained as follows:

$$h_{HNN} = \max(0, \gamma \hat{z}_{HNN} + \beta) \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{z}_{HNN} = W_{HNN}[h_{LSTM}, h_{MLP}] + b_{HNN}$ and γ and β are trainable parameters of the model.

The outcome of the network is computed using the sigmoid activation, providing a score between 0 and 1. This score can be interpreted as the probability that there is an NTL in the SM, though its confidence strength depends on the strength of regularization [29]:

$$P_{NTL} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(W_{NTL}h_{HNN} + b_{NTL})}} \quad (10)$$

where P_{NTL} represents the probability that there is an NTL in the SM. W_{NTL} and b_{NTL} represent the trainable weights and bias of the output layer.

IV. LEARNING AND EVALUATION

A. Loss function and optimization

The performance of the model has been evaluated with the logarithmic loss function, as this is a binary classification task:

$$L = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M -(y_i \log(P_{NTL}^i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - P_{NTL}^i)) \quad (11)$$

where M is the number of customer samples, y_i is the ground-truth label and P_{NTL}^i is the probability of NTL computed by the HNN-NTL model for the customer sample i .

The trainable parameters of the model have been initialized with a Xavier initialization [30] and optimized to minimize the loss function using the Adam optimizer [31], a first-order gradient-based optimization method.

B. Metrics for evaluation

One of the main challenges of tackling the NTL detection problem with a supervised approach is the imbalance between classes. A suitable metric for NTL detection is the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC-AUC) [32]. The ROC curve is obtained by plotting the true positive rate (TPR), also known as recall, against the false positive rate (FPR) by varying the decision threshold on the predictions. The score ranges between 0 and 1, a score above 0.5 being obtained with better than random predictions. Though the TPR and FPR are valuable metrics when assessing the performance of a model for NTL detection, they do not account for the precision of the model. A metric suitable for imbalanced datasets that takes into account the precision of the model is the area under the precision-recall curve (PR-AUC) [33], [34]. We therefore decided to use the PR-AUC metric for the model selection on the validation dataset, as taking into account the success rate of the on-field inspections is extremely important for the utilities, for economic reasons (a limited budget for on-field inspections leads to a limited number of inspections per year, for which the success rate is required to be maximized).

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Data availability

All the models have been trained and tested on real SM data of Endesa, the largest electricity utility in Spain. The data provided by the utility have been anonymized and a noise of approximately 5 km has been added to the geographical coordinates. All samples in the dataset have a contracted power below 15 kW.

The labeled dataset that is used for training consists of SMs had at least one on-field inspection. To analyze the capability of the model to generalize beyond its training dataset, the original data have been split into a training, validation and test dataset. The split has been done in a stratified manner, so that there is the same % of NTL samples in each dataset. The training dataset consists of 80 % of the labeled dataset, whilst the validation and test datasets consist of ≈ 10 % each. Table III shows the number of samples in each dataset as well as their % of NTL samples.

TABLE III
LABELED DATASET

Dataset type	Number of samples	% of NTL samples
Training	85226	13.34%
Validation	10612	13.50%
Test	10701	13.23%

As can be seen in Table III, the dataset is highly imbalanced which can make the model biased to probabilities closer to 0. However, this doesn't have a strong negative impact on our model as the metrics employed assess the ranking of samples rather than the confidence strength of their probabilities.

B. Data processing

The weekly profile, zero measurements and missing measurements have been normalized separately, using their maximum value:

$$f(x) = \frac{x}{\max(x)} \quad (12)$$

The season did not require any normalization, as it was one-hot-encoded.

In the case of non-sequential features, the missing values in non-categorical features were replaced with the mean. For categorical features, a special "Unknown" category has been created to replace missing data. After imputing the missing data, the non-sequential features were standardized to have 0 mean and unit variance using the following formula:

$$f(x) = \frac{x - \bar{x}}{s} \quad (13)$$

where \bar{x} represents the mean of the input feature and s represents the standard deviation.

C. Implementation

Given the large size of the dataset, all the data exploration and processing have been done with open source software PySpark [35], taking advantage of distributed computing using a cluster of machines. All neural networks were built and trained using TensorFlow [36], an open-source deep learning framework. For the comparison with state-of-the-art ML algorithms, the Scikit-learn [37] library has been used to fit the models. For extreme gradient boosted trees [38], the model has been fitted using its Python API.

D. Experiment hyperparameters

The performance of a machine learning algorithm depends strongly on its hyperparameters. As it was seen in Figure 4, the size of the HNN-NTL network can be adjusted by controlling the size of various hidden layers such as h_{LSTM} and h_{HNN} . A grid-search has been implemented in order to find the best hyperparameters. Table IV shows the range of values searched as well as the optimal value found. The optimal value was found by monitoring the performance of the validation dataset. As a regularization method, a dropout layer has been used on the output of the h_{LSTM} , h_{MLP} , h_{HNN} and every h_i layer of the MLP module. No regularization has been used on the LSTM cell h_{CELL} , as it did not improve the performance of the model.

TABLE IV
HNN-NTL HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Hyperparameter	Range of values	Optimal value
N	4, 6	4
Size h_i	256, 512	256
Size h_{CELL}	256, 512	256
Size h_{LSTM}	256, 512	512
Size h_{MLP}	256, 512	512
Size h_{HNN}	1024, 2048	1024
Dropout	0.3, 0.5	0.3

E. LSTM module results

In order to assess the performance in particular of the LSTM module (only sequential data), an experiment was performed with a simplified network where the MLP module and the h_{HNN} layer of Figure 4 were omitted.

1) *LSTM with the weekly profile*: Figure 5 shows the performance of the LSTM model when using as input only the weekly profile. As can be seen in Figures 6 and 7, a PR-AUC of 0.33 and a ROC-AUC score of 0.72 have been obtained on the test dataset. Even with such simple input, the model significantly outperforms random predictions.

2) *LSTM with all data*: Figures 8, 9 and 10 show the model performance of the LSTM model when using all input data (weekly profile, zero measurements, missing measurements

Fig. 5. Simple LSTM model performance during training

Fig. 6. PR curve of simple LSTM model using the best trained model

Fig. 7. ROC curve of simple LSTM model using the best trained model

Fig. 10. ROC curve of LSTM model using the best trained model

Fig. 8. LSTM model performance during training

Fig. 11. HNN-NTL model performance during training

Fig. 9. PR curve of LSTM model using the best trained model

Fig. 12. PR curve of HNN-NTL model using the best trained model

and season). By using this additional data, the PR-AUC has increased from 0.33 to 0.41 on the test dataset.

F. HNN-NTL model results

The performance of the HNN-NTL model can be seen in Figures 11, 12 and 13. As can be seen, the HNN-NTL model greatly outperforms the LSTM model, obtaining a PR-AUC score of 0.54 on the test dataset. As expected, using non-sequential features such as the contracted power or the SM model dramatically improves the performance for NTL detection.

Fig. 13. ROC curve of HNN-NTL model using the best trained model

G. Comparison

In this section, we will compare the performance of the HNN-NTL model with state-of-the-art classifiers as well as previous deep learning approaches. As all the models described below require a fixed size input, we have used a fixed size window of one year on the sequential data.

1) *Support Vector Machines*: The support vector machine (SVM) is a very popular classifier for NTL detection. The objective of this algorithm is to find an optimal hyperplane that maximizes the margin between the vectors of the distinct classes [39].

Table V shows the range of hyperparameters used during grid-search as well as their optimal value found on the validation dataset. A linear kernel has been used due to the size of the dataset.

TABLE V
SVM HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Hyperparameter	Range of values	Optimal value
C	0.001, 0.01, 10, 100	0.001

2) *Logistic Regression*: Logistic regression (LR) is a popular supervised algorithm for binary classification tasks, that uses the same principles as neural networks. To obtain the probability of NTL for a sample, the algorithm multiplies the input features with a matrix of trained weights and passes the output through the sigmoid function [40]. The optimal weights were found using the logarithmic loss function and the LIBLINEAR solver [41]. Table VI shows the hyperparameters used during grid-search for LR.

TABLE VI
LR HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Hyperparameter	Range of values	Optimal value
C	0.001, 0.01, 10, 100	0.001
R	L1 norm, L2 norm	L2 norm

3) *Random Forests*: Random forests (RF) fall into the category of ensemble models [42]. The algorithm combines several decision trees (DT) to create a collection of trees that can make more accurate predictions. The mode of the predictions of individual trees is used in order to output a final decision. Table VII shows the hyperparameters used during grid-search for RF.

TABLE VII
RF HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Hyperparameter	Range of values	Optimal value
Number of trees	1000, 2000	1000
Minimum samples split	5, 10, 15	10
Maximum depth	7, 15	15
Minimum samples leaf	5, 10, 15	15

4) *Extreme Gradient Boosted Trees*: Extreme gradient boosted trees (XGB) is a very popular algorithm in the data science community, winning many competitions on the data science platform Kaggle [43]. It has already been used successfully for NTL detection [15]. The algorithm uses gradient

boosting [44] with a regularized loss function which makes the model less prone to overfitting and increases its generalization capabilities on new samples. Gradient boosted learning is a very powerful machine learning technique which combines several DT to create a collection of trees that can make more accurate predictions. Table VIII shows the hyperparameters used during grid-search as well as the optimal value found.

TABLE VIII
XGB HYPERPARAMETERS SEARCH

Hyperparameter	Range of values	Optimal value
Number of trees	1000, 2000	1000
Learning rate	0.01, 0.1	0.01
Maximum depth	7, 15	7
Minimum child weight	1, 5, 10	10

5) *Multi-Layer Perceptrons Networks*: MLP networks have already been used successfully in NTL detection [20], [21]. In this comparison, we use the same architecture and hyperparameters of the MLP module from our HNN-NTL model. This MLP network has in addition input features extracted from the raw EC data.

6) *Convolutional Neural Networks*: CNN have been shown to outperform stacked autoencoders and LSTM networks, in [22], on a dataset with synthetic NTL samples. We used the same architecture proposed in [22], as well as the same hyperparameters that have been used in their experiment. The original experiment used monthly EC data as an input to the CNN network but we have increased the granularity to daily EC measurements given our data availability.

7) *Wide & Deep Convolutional Neural Networks*: The wide & deep convolutional neural network (WD-CNN) is a deep learning architecture for NTL detection proposed by the authors in [23]. The algorithm uses a Wide network (equivalent to a MLP network) on the 1D daily EC data and a CNN on the 2D stacked weekly energy profiles. We used the same hyperparameters that were used in their experiments, therefore a grid-search has not been performed for this model. The special convolution kernel has also been implemented using a hyperbolic tangent activation function.

8) *Results*: This section shows the results obtained for the comparison of the HNN-NTL algorithm with other state-of-the-art classifiers. The same training, validation and test datasets described in Table III have been used for all the models in this comparison. The input that was used for the SVM, LR, RF, XGB and MLP models is shown in Table IX. As mentioned previously, these algorithms require a fixed size input, thus we have retrieved from each customer sample the daily EC of the past year. The auxiliary data input is equivalent to the same input used in the MLP module of the HNN-NTL model. The same entity embeddings have been used for the categorical features. The EC input consists of the same information that has been used in the LSTM module, but restricted to the EC of the previous year.

The CNN network uses as input only the 1D daily EC data, as can be seen in Table X.

TABLE IX
SVM, LR, RF, XGB AND MLP INPUT

Input	Description	Size
Auxiliary data	Latitude	1
	Longitude	1
	Altitude	1
	Municipality	5
	Contracted power	1
	Contract type	2
	Voltage	1
	SM model	3
	SM location	3
	SM firmware version	3
	SM production year	3
	Economic activity code	10
	EC input	Daily EC consumption
Daily zero measurements		260
Daily missing measurements		260

TABLE X
CNN INPUT

Input	Description	Size
CNN input	1D daily EC consumption of last year.	260

The input for the WD-CNN algorithm can be found in Table XI. As described in [23], the algorithm uses only the EC data as an input. For the Wide module, the input is simply the daily energy consumption of the past year. To create the input for the CNN module, the daily EC consumption has been divided into weekly profiles and stacked into a 2D array. The weekly profiles were stacked starting with the first week of the year up until the last.

TABLE XI
WD-CNN INPUT

Input	Description	Size
Wide input	Daily EC consumption of last year.	260
CNN input	Weekly EC profiles of last year.	260

Table XII shows the results of the comparison, for various sizes of the training dataset. Deep learning models are known to be sensitive to the size of the dataset used during training. Therefore, this analysis shows whether the HNN-NTL model maintains its superiority when less training samples are available. As can be seen, the HNN-NTL model vastly outperforms any other algorithm, for both PR-AUC and ROC-AUC metrics and for all sizes of the training dataset.

TABLE XII
FINAL PR-AUC AND ROC-AUC RESULTS ON THE TEST DATASET

Methods	Training = 40%		Training = 60%		Training = 80%	
	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC
Random	0.5	0.133	0.5	0.133	0.5	0.133
SVM	0.710	0.277	0.714	0.281	0.716	0.284
LR	0.715	0.282	0.718	0.285	0.719	0.285
RF	0.744	0.331	0.751	0.340	0.753	0.345
XGB	0.767	0.377	0.776	0.391	0.777	0.394
MLP	0.738	0.314	0.723	0.263	0.685	0.246
CNN	0.689	0.244	0.681	0.244	0.654	0.213
WD-CNN	0.672	0.263	0.690	0.276	0.687	0.276
HNN-NTL	0.822	0.520	0.813	0.499	0.836	0.545

For traditional classifiers such as SVM and RF the per-

formance always increases with increased data availability. For the WD-CNN and HNN-NTL models, the performance is either increasing or decreasing which suggests that a new grid-search on hyperparameters should be performed on each size of the training dataset for optimal results.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a hybrid model for non-technical losses detection. To our knowledge, this is the first deep learning approach that is able to incorporate both sequential and non-sequential data. We have shown that by integrating auxiliary data, significant improvements in the performance of the model are achieved. The model has obtained a PR-AUC of 0.545 and a ROC-AUC score of 0.836 on the test dataset. Comparison with other state-of-the-art classifiers has shown that the proposed hybrid neural network model is able to surpass the performance of very powerful classifiers such as extreme gradient boosted trees. The methodology has been developed and tested with real smart meter data of Endesa, the largest electricity utility in Spain. It is currently used as a non-technical losses detection tool in the utility, obtaining a precision of $\approx 47\%$ for new on-field inspections generated by our ranked list of customers.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Endesa for funding this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] CIRED, "Reduction of Technical and Non-Technical Losses in Distribution Networks," 2017.
- [2] C. León, F. Biscarri, I. Monedero, J. I. Guerrero, J. Biscarri, and R. Millán, "Variability and trend-based generalized rule induction model to NTL detection in power companies," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1798–1807, 2011.
- [3] P. Glauner, J. A. Meira, P. Valtchev, R. State, and F. Bettinger, "The Challenge of Non-Technical Loss Detection Using Artificial Intelligence: A Survey," *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 760, 1 2017.
- [4] S. S. S. R. Depuru, L. Wang, and V. Devabhaktuni, "Electricity theft: Overview, issues, prevention and a smart meter based approach to control theft," *Energy Policy*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 1007–1015, 2 2011.
- [5] L. northeast group, "Electricity Theft and Non-Technical Losses: Global Markets, Solutions, and Vendors," Tech. Rep., 2017.
- [6] L. Arango, E. Deccache, B. D. Bonatto, H. Arango, P. Ribeiro, and P. M. Silveira, "Impact of electricity theft on power quality," in *2016 17th International Conference on Harmonics and Quality of Power (ICHQP)*. IEEE, 10 2016, pp. 557–562.
- [7] A. Fragkioudaki, P. Cruz-Romero, A. Gómez-Expósito, J. Biscarri, M. J. de Tellechea, and A. Arcos, "Detection of Non-technical Losses in Smart Distribution Networks: A Review." Springer, Cham, 2016, pp. 43–54.
- [8] G. M. Messinis and N. D. Hatzigiorgiour, "Review of non-technical loss detection methods," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 158, pp. 250–266, 2018.
- [9] Y. L. Lo, S. C. Huang, and C. N. Lu, "Non-technical loss detection using smart distribution network measurement data," *2012 IEEE Innovative Smart Grid Technologies - Asia, ISGT Asia 2012*, pp. 1–5, 2012.
- [10] S.-c. Huang, Y.-l. Lo, and C.-n. Lu, "Non-Technical Loss Detection Using State Estimation and Analysis of Variance," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 2959–2966, 2013.
- [11] N. G. Bretas, A. S. Bretas, S. Gazzana, S. Carlos, and R. D. P. Martin, "Non-Technical Losses Identification Using Optimum- Path Forest and State Estimation," *PowerTech*, no. June, 2015.
- [12] A. H. Nizar, Z. Y. Dong, and Y. Wang, "Power utility nontechnical loss analysis with extreme learning machine method," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 946–955, 2008.

- [13] N. F. Avila, G. Figueroa, and C. C. Chu, "NTL Detection in electric distribution systems using the maximal overlap discrete wavelet-packet transform and random undersampling boosting," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 7171–7180, 2018.
- [14] J. I. Guerrero, I. Monedero, F. Biscarri, J. Biscarri, R. Millan, and C. Leon, "Non-Technical Losses Reduction by Improving the Inspections Accuracy in a Power Utility," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 8950, no. c, pp. 1–11, 2017.
- [15] M.-M. Buzau, J. Tejedor-Aguilera, P. Cruz-Romero, and A. Gomez-Exposito, "Detection of Non-Technical Losses Using Smart Meter Data and Supervised Learning," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [16] T. J. Bihl and S. Hajjar, "Electricity theft concerns within advanced energy technologies," in *2017 IEEE National Aerospace and Electronics Conference (NAECON)*. IEEE, 6 2017, pp. 271–278.
- [17] S. S. S. R. Depuru, L. Wang, V. Devabhaktuni, and P. Nelapati, "A hybrid neural network model and encoding technique for enhanced classification of energy consumption data," *IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting*, pp. 1–8, 2011.
- [18] . Monedero, F. Biscarri, C. León, J. Biscarri, and R. Millán, "MIDAS: Detection of non-technical losses in electrical consumption using neural networks and statistical techniques," *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 3984 LNCS, pp. 725–734, 2006.
- [19] J. I. Guerrero, C. León, I. Monedero, F. Biscarri, and J. Biscarri, "Improving Knowledge-Based Systems with statistical techniques, text mining, and neural networks for non-technical loss detection," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 71, pp. 376–388, 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2014.08.014>
- [20] B. C. Costa, B. L. a. Alberto, A. M. Portela, W. Maduro, O. Eler, and B. Horizonte, "Fraud Detection in Electric Power Distribution Networks Using an ANN-Based Knowledge-Discovery Process," *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Applications (IJAIA)*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 17–23, 2013.
- [21] L. A. M. Pereira, L. C. S. Afonso, J. P. Papa, Z. A. Vale, C. C. O. Ramos, D. S. Gastaldello, and A. N. Souza, "Multilayer perceptron neural networks training through charged system search and its Application for non-technical losses detection," *2013 IEEE PES Conference on Innovative Smart Grid Technologies, ISGT LA 2013*, 2013.
- [22] R. R. Bhat, R. D. Trevizan, R. Sengupta, X. Li, and A. Bretas, "Identifying Nontechnical Power Loss via Spatial and Temporal Deep Learning," in *2016 15th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA)*. IEEE, 12 2016, pp. 272–279.
- [23] Z. Zheng, Y. Yang, X. Niu, H.-N. Dai, and Y. Zhou, "Wide and Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Electricity-Theft Detection to Secure Smart Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1606–1615, 4 2018.
- [24] J. Elman, "Finding Structure in Time," *COGNITIVE SCIENCE*, vol. 14, pp. 179–211, 1990.
- [25] R. Pascanu, T. Mikolov, and Y. Bengio, "On the difficulty of training recurrent neural networks," *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 1310–1318, 2013.
- [26] S. Hochreiter and J. J. Urgan Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
- [27] C. Guo and F. Berkahn, "Entity Embeddings of Categorical Variables," Tech. Rep.
- [28] S. Ioffe and C. Szegedy, "Batch Normalization: Accelerating Deep Network Training by Reducing Internal Covariate Shift," 2 2015.
- [29] A. Karpathy, L. Fei-Fei, and J. Johnson, "CS231n: Convolutional neural networks for visual recognition," 2016.
- [30] X. Glorot and Y. Bengio, "Understanding the difficulty of training deep feedforward neural networks," Tech. Rep.
- [31] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, "Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization," 12 2014.
- [32] P. O. Glauner, A. Boechat, L. Dolberg, R. State, F. Bettinger, Y. Rangoni, and D. Duarte, "Large-Scale Detection of Non-Technical Losses in Imbalanced Data Sets," pp. 1–5, 2016.
- [33] J. Davis and M. Goadrich, "The Relationship Between Precision-Recall and ROC Curves," Tech. Rep.
- [34] V. Raghavan, P. Bollmann, and G. S. Jung, "A critical investigation of recall and precision as measures of retrieval system performance," *ACM Transactions on Information Systems*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 205–229, 7 1989.
- [35] M. Zaharia, M. Chowdhury, M. J. Franklin, S. Shenker, and I. Stoica, "Spark: cluster computing with working sets," pp. 10–10, 2010.
- [36] M. Abadi, A. Agarwal, P. Barham, E. Brevdo, Z. Chen, C. Citro, G. S. Corrado, A. Davis, J. Dean, M. Devin, S. Ghemawat, I. Goodfellow, A. Harp, G. Irving, M. Isard, Y. Jia, R. Jozefowicz, L. Kaiser, M. Kudr, J. Levenberg, D. Mané, R. Monga, S. Moore, D. Murray, C. Olah, M. Schuster, J. Shlens, B. Steiner, I. Sutskever, K. Talwar, P. Tucker, V. Vanhoucke, V. Vasudevan, F. Viégas, O. Vinyals, P. Warden, M. Wattenberg, M. Wicke, Y. Yu, X. Zheng, and G. Research, "TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Distributed Systems," Tech. Rep.
- [37] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and . Duchesnay, "Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python," *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [38] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost : A Scalable Tree Boosting System," *22nd ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016.
- [39] C. Cortes and V. Vapnik, "Support-Vector Networks," *Machine Learning*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 273–297, 1995.
- [40] A. Ng. Machine learning. Course Lecture. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coursera.org/learn/machine-learning>
- [41] R.-E. Fan, K.-W. Chang, C.-J. Hsieh, X.-R. Wang, and C.-J. Lin, "LIBLINEAR: A library for large linear classification," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 9, pp. 1871–1874, 2008.
- [42] L. Breiman and Leo, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, 2001.
- [43] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System," in *22nd ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016.
- [44] J. H. Friedman, "Greedy Function Approximation: A Gradient Boosting Machine," *The Annals of Statistics*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 1189–1232, 2001.

Madalina-Mihaela Buzau received her BEng in Power Systems from Politehnica University of Bucharest and her MRes in Electrical Engineering and Sustainable Development from Lille University of Science and Technology. She is now pursuing a Ph.D. degree in the Department of Electrical Engineering of the University of Seville. Her main research focus is on the usage of smart meter data and machine learning algorithms for non-technical loss detection in the utilities.

Javier Tejedor Aguilera received the telecommunication engineering degree from the University of Seville, Spain. He is currently the Endesa Distribución responsible for non-technical losses detection. His primary areas of interest are data science, machine learning and deep learning. He is an active participant in machine learning competitions.

Pedro Cruz-Romero (M06) received the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering from the University of Seville, Spain, in 2000. Currently, he is an Associate Professor. His primary areas of interest are magnetic-field mitigation and transmission and distribution operation and planning.

Antonio Gómez-Expósito (F'05) received the electrical engineering and doctor degrees from the University of Seville, Spain, where he is currently the Endesa Red Industrial Chair Professor. His primary areas of interest are optimal power system operation, state estimation, digital signal processing and control of flexible ac transmission system devices.

Point-By-Point Reply to Reviewers' Comments

Thank you, everyone, for taking the time to review our revised paper. The point-by-point reply to the editor and reviewers' comments is given below.

Editor's Comments:

Editor

Comments to the Author:

Reviewers present major concerns in regards to potential scientific contributions of the work towards the state of the art. It is not clear what are the scientific contributions of the work towards the state of the art.

- Thank you so much for giving us the opportunity to revise the paper and emphasize its scientific contributions. We have expanded the related work section, to give a better idea of how our work differentiates itself from previous approaches. We also added new models in the comparison in order to have a more thorough analysis. The main scientific contribution of this paper is that we presented a methodology for NTL detection that doesn't rely on any expert knowledge and that significantly outperforms all the related previous approaches.
-

Reviewers' Comments:

Reviewer: 1

Comments to the Author

The paper presents a new approach to detect non-technical losses (NTL) in smart meters (SM). The approach considers both sequential and non-sequential data, the first one analyzed by a long short-term memory network and the second one by a multilayer perceptron network. The networks are then combined to obtain a score between 0 and 1 interpreted as the probability that there is an NTL in the SM, making possible to create a rank list of suspect consumers.

The paper presents comparison results with many other state-of-art methods considering real data, demonstrating that the proposed method is more reliable than others. However, it is not possible to replicate the study, since the SM data are not available. Being this a characteristic of many NTL detection papers. It is recommended to provide the data or also perform a comparative study case considering a test system with available data, allowing result verification by other researchers. A test system example is presented in Distribution Test System for Nontechnical Loss Detection (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8600553>).

- Thank you so much for your suggestion. Ideally this data would have been published along with the paper. We have tried to obtain an authorization to make this data public

but it wasn't accepted. We think that the biggest proof that showcases the success of this methodology is that it has been used to generate new inspections and improved ~3.5 times the precision of previous on-field inspections.

- We are very grateful to the authors in "Distribution Test System for Nontechnical Loss Detection", for providing a benchmark dataset for NTL detection. Since the HNN-NTL model uses both energy consumption data and auxiliary data (SM model, contract type etc.) it cannot be tested on the benchmark dataset which consists only of energy consumption data. The disadvantage of the benchmark dataset is that it creates synthetical NTL samples that consists either in partial or total load reduction whilst the non-NTL samples have normal consumption patterns. However, in the real environment, customer can have partial or total reduction due to causes that are not related to NTL such as going on a holiday. This is why we believe it is vital to use auxiliary data, as we cannot rely simply on the energy consumption data.

Regarding the contributions, the items:

"We investigate the boost in performance obtained by combining both types of data and show that the hybrid network significantly outperforms a network that uses only EC data as an input. We show that the proposed architecture vastly outperforms the previous NTL detection model that was based on deep learning and raw data. We also compare its performance with state-of-the-art classifiers and their learning capabilities with raw SM data."

In my point of view, it is not a state-of-art contribution, but the result of the study case performed. It was not analytically demonstrated that this approach outperforms the others.

- We have shown empirically that the methodology proposed outperformed previous methods. The performance of a machine learning algorithm over the other depends strongly on the type of dataset that is used as an input. Hence there is no universal proof that an ML algorithm outperforms another in every scenario. We did show however, through experiments, that the HNN-NTL model outperforms the rest of classifiers on smart meter data that belongs to spanish customers and for the NTL detection task.

Also, methods that combine data-driven approach with system analysis method to detect NTL were not mentioned, as examples:

Non-technical losses identification using Optimum-Path Forest and state estimation (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7232685>);

Non-Technical Loss Detection Using State Estimation and Analysis of Variance (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6490071>).

- Thank you for your suggestion. We did not mention the papers mentioned above, as they are a different area of research. However, taking into consideration your opinion, we have created a new "Related work" section which includes the hybrid-oriented methods that you have mentioned above.

In "Fig. 1.", please discuss better each figure. For example, in which hour the NTL start for each case?

- That is a great idea. We have added a marker on each figure to showcase where the NTL has started. We also improved the explanation of each NTL case, in the Motivation section.

In the sentence “The first step is to create customer samples using the SM and auxiliary data. Data processing techniques such as normalization, label indexing and categorical embeddings have been used for each customer sample in part.” Although a reference is cited [12], the paper must be intelligible by itself, please add a brief summary of these data processing techniques.

- The data processing techniques are described in Section V.B so we have added a reference to that section, in case the reader wishes to learn more about these techniques, at that stage.

In fig. 2 appears “first and last day of each customer sample”. It is not described in the text and not clear how it is considered in the proposed method. Please, make it more clear

- Thank you for your feedback. We obtain the first and last day of each customer sample, using the procedure that we described in our previous paper. To accommodate your request, we have provided an in-depth explanation on how they were obtained in the Methodology section. We also added a new figure (Figure 3) which shows an example of how **are we** extracting customer samples, using the case of a customer who had multiple inspections throughout its contract.

The Fig. 5 to 9 are too small. Please, review these figures.

- Thank you for letting us know. We have increased the size of these figures to make them more readable. Hope this helps!

Overall, we are grateful for all the suggestions you have made to improve this paper. We have tried to implement them as much as we could and we truly believe that the current state of the paper has improved thanks to you.

Reviewer: 2

Comments to the Author

This paper presents a Hybrid neural network (HNN) approach to the problem of detection of non-technical losses (NTL) on power systems. This approach uses both sequential smart meter data and auxiliary data about the smart meter (location, type of meter, etc.). The method is tested using real data from a utility in Spain and results show it outperforms other data-driven methods.

The reviewer has some clarifying questions:

1) From my understanding, the HNN-NTL model architecture shown in Figure 3 is being run for each smart meter on the system, where the output is the probability that that specific smart meter has NTL on it for that week (since we are feeding a weekly profile). In the MLP module, it seems that all of the input data is static for a given smart meter, i.e. the location, make and model, contracted power will not change very often, certainly not each week. Because of this, the reviewer questions the utility of the MLP module as it seems it will always have the same output given the same inputs. Is this simply a way to determine which data is most important in the detection of NTL? Please discuss the value of the MLP module in more depth.

- The HNN-NTL model outputs a single probability of having NTL in the SM, at the end of the customer sample, not on a weekly basis. The LSTM module sees the entire EC history, week by week, and it provides a single final output, h_T , which is the hidden state of the LSTM cell at the final time step (last week of the sample). The h_T is afterwards concatenated with the output of the MLP module. Thus, the MLP module sees the static data only once, not week by week.
- We have updated Figure 4 to make this more clear. We have also expanded Section III.B with additional info.

2) What was the reasoning behind using weekly profiles for the LSTM module? Also, does this mean we run this only once a week? Could it be possible for a daily run to catch more NTL problems if customers are trying to be stealthy? This doesn't seem unreasonable in the context of NTL and maybe the utility only requests a weekly query, but could the authors explain this decision for clarity to the reader?

- The HNN-NTL model is run only once per customer sample. For example, let's say we have a customer sample that started in June 2017 and ends in May 2019. The HNN-NTL model will output a probability that the customer has NTL detection in May 2019. This is because we are interested if the customer is committing fraud or has an anomaly in the present, not in the past.
- We have added this explanation in the paper, to answer your question and make it more clear for the reader as well: "We decided to use the weekly profile as input to the LSTM, rather than the daily consumption, in order to reduce the number of time steps through the network. By reducing the number of time steps, the network is able to learn faster. Using the weekly profile gives the network the opportunity to detect more complex types of NTL, such as intermittent NTL, which occurs only on some certain days of the week. These cases would be much more difficult to detect when using only the monthly energy consumption as an input."

3) The authors mention that this method is being used by Endesa with a precision of 47% for new on-field inspections. Could the authors expand on the meaning of this metric and how it relates to the other results shown (ROC, PR, etc.)? Also, how does this compare to the precision of new on-field inspections without this method?

- Thank you for your suggestion. We have added this explanation in the paper to reduce any uncertainty: "The precision is the fraction of SMs that were actually identified with NTL among the total number of SMs that have been inspected using the ranked list of

customers provided by our model. This methodology is currently used as an NTL detection tool in the utility, achieving a precision of $\approx 47\%$ for new on-field inspections generated by our model. This represents a 3.5 times improvement over the precision of previous on-field inspections that have been generated through other tools and campaigns.”

Thank you so much for your feedback. We have revised the paper according to your suggestions and we are hopeful that it has made our methodology clearer and easier to understand.

Reviewer: 3

Comments to the Author

The authors propose a hybrid classifier for nontechnical loss detection that uses a three-layer neural network to combine the outputs of a LSTM and a MLP modules. The paper is very well written. However, despite citing a few survey papers, the literature review requires significant improvement and more details should be given to make the comparison section more clear.

The suggestions for improving the quality of the paper are condensed in the following items:

1. The literature review is insufficient. One Deep Learning-based approach is used as a benchmark, but other closely related methods were left out, such as [A1-A5]. How does your method compare to these?

[A1] Multilayer perceptron neural networks training through charged system search and its application for non-technical losses detection

[A2] Identifying nontechnical power loss via spatial and temporal deep learning

[A3] Midas: Detection of non-technical losses in electrical consumption using neural networks and statistical techniques

[A4] Improving knowledge-based systems with statistical techniques, text mining, and neural networks for non-technical loss detection.

[A5] A Hybrid Neural Network Model and Encoding Technique for Enhanced Classification of Energy Consumption Data

- Thank you for your input. Following your advice, we have created a “Related work” section in the paper to provide a better context and comparison for our paper. We have included in this section all the papers mentioned above. Though all these papers use neural networks (NN) in their methodology, not all of them as a classifier for NTL detection. For example, [A5] uses NN to choose the best hyperparameters of the Support Vector Machines classifier used for NTL detection. The work in [A4] uses NN to automatically classify concepts extracted from inspectors’ comments of previous on-field inspections. The authors in [A3] use NN in an unsupervised manner which is a different area of research. [A1] and [A2] were closely related methods to our work so we have

added them in the comparison section as well. As you will see, in the comparison section we have added a MLP network (as in [A1]) and a CNN network (as in [A2]).

2. The flowchart of Fig. 2 should be revised. In it, the Unlabeled Dataset is never processed before joining the labeled dataset preprocessed during model evaluation.

- Thank you so much for your suggestion. We did revise the flowchart so that it reflects better the data processing steps. We changed “Data processing” -> “Creating customer samples” as this is the first data processing technique that occurs before splitting the dataset into a labeled and unlabeled dataset. We added the “Data processing” step after splitting the labeled data into a training, validation and test dataset in order to have available the statistics of the training dataset that we need for normalization. This step is performed on both labeled and unlabeled datasets. Though the label indexing, categorical embeddings and the normalization of the load curve can be done when creating the customer samples, the normalization and imputation of non-sequential features (SM model, latitude etc.) can be done only after creating the training dataset. The revised flowchart reflects now better the entire process.
- We also improved the flowchart description with additional information as well as discussing in more depth how the customer samples are created for each individual in part. Hope this helps!

3. Auxiliary data is mentioned in the second but is not defined until the last but one page.

- The auxiliary data is used in the MLP input. We have added explanations in the flowchart to specify this. We also added a brief description in the text, in order to define it: “auxiliary data (geographical, contracts, technical and economic data)”.

4. Some figures are hard to read due to their small size.

- Thank you for letting us know. We now increased their size so we really hope that they're easier to read.

5. Logistic regression is a very elementary method. Why use it as a benchmark?

- We agree that logistic regression is a rather simple machine learning algorithm. However, given its similarity with neural networks, we thought it is only fair to introduce it in the comparison. For many types of problems and datasets, it is sufficient to use a simple logistic regression rather than a big neural network that uses so much more resources and computational power. So we wanted to make sure that this was not the case for our problem. But we do appreciate your opinion on this.

6. There are many unclear aspects with respect to the performance comparison of the methods, especially when it comes to the data used for training and evaluating. In your comparison, how much data have you used to train your method?

- The description of the entire labeled dataset can be found in Table III. In this table, we give the exact dimensions of the training, validation and test dataset. The training dataset has 85226 samples, the validation dataset has 10612 samples and the test

dataset has 10701 samples. We've done a 80%-10%-10% split. We also made sure to separate the labeled dataset in a stratified manner, so that the same proportion of NTL ~13.3% is found in all three datasets. The percentage of samples found with NTL of each dataset can be found as well in Table III.

Is is the same as for other methods?

- Absolutely. For a fair comparison, the same training, validation and test dataset have been used for all classifiers and for our models. We have added this mention in the comparison section for clarity.

Why choose one year of data?

- All the models used in the comparison, except ours, cannot handle variable sized inputs. Let's say that a customer has SM measurements for 3 months and another customer for 6 months. We cannot use as an input to a SVM for example, samples with different sizes. So in this case, we will have to restrict the input to 3 months. However, the first customer might have had the inspection in February whilst the second one in October. If we take the consumption of their last 3 months, they won't have as an input the same period of time. To avoid this, we use as an input one year of data, in order to make sure the input is the same for everyone. We could have chosen as input two years of data but this would have discarded a lot of samples as many customers have SM measurements for less than two years. Moreover, this would have also introduced a longer delay in NTL detection. The customer must have had at least 2 years of SM measurements and if the SM had an inspection, that inspection should have been at least 2 years ago.
- This is one of the main advantage of the model that we propose in this paper. The LSTM module can receive a sample with 3 months of EC measurements and the next sample with 6 months of EC measurements. This way, the network sees the entire consumption profile as it is not restricted to a fixed size input.

What was passed on as an input to these classifiers?

- The input to the SVM, LR, RF, XGB and MLP classifiers can be found in Table IX. We improved the table by having each feature individually on a row, as well as adding its input size. As you will notice, the input to these classifiers is very similar to the HNN-NTL model. We used all the features that the MLP module of the HNN-NTL model uses. Since we couldn't use the same input from the LSTM module due to the variable lengths of the samples, we took the last year of EC from each customer sample, removed the weekends, and retrieved the daily energy consumption, daily zero measurements and daily missing measurements. It is the same input that was used in the LSTM module, now restricted to the last year consumption, to accommodate the fixed size input requirement of these classifiers.
- The input for the CNN model simply consists of 1D energy consumption data, as in the original paper, and can be found in Table X. Furthermore, the input for the WD-CNN model can be found in Table XI. It uses only the energy consumption data as in their original paper. We simply replicated their input. It uses the daily energy consumption as

it is, in a fully-connected neural network and stacked in a 2D manner week by week as an input to the convolutional neural network module.

- We also added more explanations of the inputs, in the paper, to make it **more clear** for the reader.

Do these benchmark classifiers also use categorical information? How was this information encoded?

- Yes, all the categorical features have been used as an input to the benchmark classifiers.
- This can be seen now more clearly in Table IX, after improving it. We have used the same entity embeddings to encode these variables, as we did in our models. We tried to make the comparison as fair as possible thus we have tried, as much as possible, that all models have the same data availability. Exception is the WD-CNN model, where we had to replicate the model used in the original paper, which used only EC data.

I acknowledge that it is hard to make a fair comparison between methods, especially when they are all designed with different availabilities of datasets and features in mind, but the amount of information you have provided in your paper is insufficient.

- Yes, we agree with you. It wasn't definitely trivial to create this comparison especially since we had to reproduce from scratch quite complex models such as WD-CNN, in addition to our models. We made this comparison as fair as possible: we used the same data for training, validation and testing for all the models and we also did a hyperparameters search for each model. We have expanded the comparison section with additional information in order to clarify any uncertainties related to the experiments.

7. Please provide further justification for using a linear kernel to the SVM. Using a linear kernel seems a very poor choice, since it assumes that the dataset is linearly separable, which does not seem likely. Using nonlinear SVM classifiers seems a better fit for this problem, which is very complex, and has been done before, like [A6-A7] among many others.

[A6] Support vector machine based data classification for detection of electricity theft

[A7] Non-technical loss analysis for detection of electricity theft using support vector machines

- We decided to use only a linear kernel for the SVM after reading [A8], where the authors say:
“Training of SVMs using a kernel to map the input to higher dimension is only feasible for a few ten thousand training examples in a realistic amount of time [6]. Therefore, for Big Data sets only a linear implementation of SVMs is practically usable [19].”
A[8] Neighborhood Features Help Detecting Non-Technical Losses in Big Data Sets
- However, to accommodate your request, we have done additional experiments in order to research whether a non-linear kernel would have a better performance on our dataset. Figures 1 and 2 show the performance obtained with a linear (default), a radial basis function and a polynomial (2nd degree) kernel. As you can see, the linear kernel seems

to be the best choice for our dataset. Figure 3 shows also the training time for each of these kernels. The training time for the linear SVM was a few seconds hence it cannot be seen in the graph.

Fig. 1. Precision-Recall curves

Fig. 2. ROC-AUC curves

Fig. 3. Computation time during training

8. It is unclear how the daily energy consumption of the weekdays is obtained from Smart Meter data.

- We have added this explanation in the paper: “The daily EC has been obtained by simply averaging the hourly ECs in a day. The weekend ECs were removed using the time stamp of each SM measurement.”

Thank you so much for your valuable feedback. We believe that the paper has improved significantly after implementing your suggestions.